

Rodent damage in ricefields of Madhya Pradesh, India

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Rodents recorded in Madhya Pradesh are bandicoot *Bandicota bengalensis* (Gray) and house rat *Rattus rattus* (Linnaeus).

We assessed losses to rodents in farmers' fields planted to rice variety Patel 85 in Jabalpur district. Number of hills and healthy and damaged tillers in 20 randomly selected 1-m² samples were recorded every 14 d. Yield loss was

Estimated yield loss to rodents in ricefields. Madhya Pradesh, India.

Fields sampled (no.)	Area sampled (ha)	Tiller damage (%)		Yield loss (%)		Average yield loss/ha (%)
		Periphery	Center	Periphery	Center	
1	5.25	6.16	3.57	6.87	4.83	5.85
2	3.16	8.34	4.28	21.41	9.86	15.63
3	11.30	6.39	4.79	27.39	6.38	16.88
4	9.85	3.09	2.43	11.30	3.27	7.28
5	7.20	5.82	2.23	17.82	4.20	11.01
6	4.96	8.33	3.88	7.22	4.72	5.97

calculated as

$$\text{Yield loss \%} = \frac{a - b}{a} \times 100$$

where a = average yield of healthy plants,

b = average yield of damaged plants.

Rodents cause 3.09 to 8.34% damage at different stages of plant growth. Yield loss was 3.3-27.4% (see table). Damage was less in the centers of fields than on the periphery, where burrows found in the bunds averaged 14.2/ha. □

Water management

Using hydrological parameters in crop planning in rainfed areas

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Hazaribagh district, situated between 23°35' to 24°45' north and 84°39' to 85°49' east, is a drought-prone rainfed area. Mean annual rainfall is 1,298.5 mm, and mean seasonal is 1,168.3 mm, with standard deviations of 286.2 mm and 271.2 mm. We studied monsoon season climate records for the last 75 yr (see table). From 1913 to 1987, the probability of annual drought was 56%, with 12% yr under severe drought, having less than 853.2 mm seasonal rainfall.

The rainfall pattern shifted after 1962, becoming less favorable to rainfed agriculturists. Although continuous drought of 34 d should occur only once in 100 yr, it occurred twice after 1962 (1966 and 1984). At 50% probability level, a 14-d maximum drought spell is expected in the late crop growth period.

The total evaporation as recorded in class A Pan evaporimeter during the 22d to the 43d standard meteorological week

Date of onset of effective monsoon period, date of termination of effective monsoon period, and length of effective monsoon period for 1913 to 1986 in Hazaribagh, Bihar, India.

Particulars	Subperiod 1, 1913-27	Subperiod 2, 1938-62	Subperiod 3, 1963-86	Total period 1913-86
Normal date of onset of effective monsoon (OEM)	18 Jun	17 Jun	18 Jun	18 Jun
Earliest OEM date	5 Jun	1 Jun	2 Jun	2 Jun
Latest OEM date	2 Jul	1 Jul	6 Jul	6 Jul
Normal date of termination of effective monsoon period (TEMP)	12 Oct	14 Oct	7 Oct	11 Oct
Earliest TEMP date	13 Sep	16 Sep	9 Sep	9 Sep
Latest TEMP date	28 Oct	27 Oct	27 Oct	28 Oct
Length of monsoon period (L)				
Normal (d)	117	121	111	117
Shortest L (d)	85	101	77	77
Longest L (d)	138	136	136	138

is 582.4 mm, with calculated 650.6 mm evapotranspiration in short-duration paddy.

Water table measurements indicate negligible groundwater contribution to the rice crop during drought spells, as water table depth is beyond 2 m.

Keeping these hydrological factors in mind, we grew upland rices of different durations in 1980-84, applying 40-8.8-16.6 kg NPK/ha. Varieties yielded increasingly better up to 110-d duration. MW10 gave highest yields. After a short-duration rice, we grew a second crop of pulse (gram) and oil seed (niger) under rainfed condition.

This research shows that with proper management and attention to hydrological parameters, farmers can grow an upland rice of up to 110-d duration, followed by an oil seed or pulse crop, in a traditionally monocropped rainfed area. □

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